

TRAINING NEEDS ASSESSMENT OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS IN MALAPATAN 1 DISTRICT TOWARDS A PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM IN ADDRESSING THE PHILIPPINE PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS FOR TEACHERS

Jay-ar M. Dubalan

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

Graduate School

General Santos City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7970729>

Published Date: 25-May-2023

Abstract: This study was aimed to assess the training needs of public-school teachers in Malapatan 1 District towards a proposed intervention program in addressing the Philippine Professional Standards for Teacher. The researchers used cross sectional survey that aimed at finding out the prevalence of the outcome of interest. Based on the findings of the study it was found out that in content knowledge and pedagogy was strongly needed while in the three domains: learning environment and diversity; curriculum and planning and assessment and reporting were much needed. It was also recommended that school heads are encouraged to consistently monitor and supervise the implementation of RPMS-PPST, Webinar Series and SLAC to address training needs of teachers and conduct School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) to teachers to all strongly needed in the four domains namely: Content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning and assessment and reporting.

Keywords: Training needs assessment, intervention program, content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners curriculum and planning assessment and reporting, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's highly globalized world, teachers need to be equipped with skills which can enhance the educational system. Teacher ought to realize that as an educator, they must engage themselves in on-depth knowledge to help the students meet the challenges and goals of education.

There are issues and problems encountered by the teachers in their field of specialization specifically in their teaching profession. On how they are going to upgrade their teaching skills, professional growth and development to be more competitive when it comes to education. According to Department of Education, the teacher's training is a big factor in the academic achievement of the students.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (79-98), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

As stated by Guevara and Nuiqui (2015), the informative allotment requires training programs and activities that would well the roles of the instructors. The responsibilities of learning have misused thoroughly as countries change their educational structure to organize students to function in today's world of rapid technological alter and globalization.

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) articulates teacher excellence through well-defined domains, strands and indicators that provide measures of proficient education, capable practice and successful commitment across teachers' career stages. This study aims to find out the priority development of teachers that can help teachers reflect on and assess their own practices as they aspire for personal growth and professional development and its perception to the implementation of Result Based Performance Management System.

As a teacher assigned in Malapatan 1 District, the researcher believes in the significance of surveying the training needs of teachers in order to make the district achieve its goals particularly in producing globally-competitive learners.

This paper aimed to identify the training needs of teachers in Malapatan 1 District as basis for the proposed intervention program in addressing Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Specifically, it sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What are the training needs of teachers on Key Result Areas namely:
 - 1.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
 - 1.2 Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners
 - 1.3 Curriculum and Planning
 - 1.4 Assessment and Reporting
2. What is the intervention program to be formulated out of the findings of the study?

This research was based on the study of Guevara and Nuiqui (2015), the educational sector requires training programs and activities that would fit the roles of the teachers. The responsibilities of learning have changed fundamentally as countries change their educational system to prepare students to function in today's world of rapid technological transform and globalization.

For Wright and Geroy (2012) believes that Training Needs Assessment should be a systematic process of collection, analysis and interpretation of data on individual, group and organizational skill gaps. It also considers the varied use of sampling techniques and data analysis.

Findings of this study would be a great help in terms of the following;

To Education Program Supervisors. The results of this study would help provide data and information about the significance of the domains and competencies of RPMS-PPST for teacher's' development. It could give guidance to educational leaders to strengthen the implementation and intensify monitoring as an opportunity for teachers' development which can be used in school levels.

To the School Heads. Results of the study could guide school heads to carefully plan on the conduct of Webinars and Learning Action Cells (LAC) in schools. This would also help them provide the mechanism for supporting new and existing members of the school's teaching staff. This study would help them to address educational issues and evaluate program effectiveness to enhance student learning.

To the Teachers. The teachers could most likely be benefited from this study mainly because they are the frontliners in all educational processes. This study would give information about the guidelines; explain mechanisms, criteria and processes for performance target setting, monitoring, evaluation and development planning. Through the RPMS, the DepEd ensures that the work hard work of teachers would focus towards achieving its vision, mission, values and planned priorities toward the delivery of excellence educational services to Filipino learners. This study would also help improve their teaching practice such as planning for classroom day to day activities, designing instructional materials and strategies.

To the Learners. Quality teaching improves learning outcomes. Thus, when teachers are equipped, teaching yields positive results on learners' performance.

To Future Researchers. Findings of this study could be the basis for future researchers to undergo the same study and focus on areas such as student achievement, organizational leadership and other educational programs.

The study was conducted in Alyeng Elementary School, Aspang Elementary School, Datu Pangolima Integrated School, Lasang Elementary School, Malapatan Central Elementary School, Malkahi Elementary School, Mama Nawa Elementary School and Sitio Lanao Elementary School for the School Year 2020-2021.

The respondents of the study were taken from the entire teacher population of Malapatan 1 District, numbering to 171 teachers.

The following terms are conceptually and operationally defined for a better understanding of the study:

Training Needs Assessment Conceptually, refers to the directorial procedure of collecting and analyzing data that supports assessment creation about when training is the best option to improve individuals' performances, define who should be qualified, and accurately what content should be taught (Clarke, 2013). Operationally, is the process of identifying the gap between performance required and current performance; performance requirements and the knowledge, skills, and abilities needed by an institution to achieve the requirements.

Intervention Program. Conceptually, a purposeful action by a human agent to create change (Midgley 2016). It is made up of the activity or activities that are provided to the targeted population, such as an educational curriculum and planning. Operationally, in this study, it illustrates the significant development structure, system and concept of the intervention program and SLAC for Malapatan 1 District based on the training needs assessment of teachers.

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. Conceptually, it refers to teachers' ability to apply mentally and with critical understanding the application of theories and principles of teaching and learning (Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers 2017). Operationally, it is the applied knowledge of teachers based on the content within and across curriculum teaching areas and teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement; it is one of the major areas to be assessed.

Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners. Conceptually, it is a learning-focused environment where teachers efficiently manage learner behavior in physical and virtual spaces. It emphasizes the importance of teacher's knowledge and understanding as well as respect for, learners' diverse characteristics and experiences as inputs to the planning and designing of learning opportunities (Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers 2017). Operationally, a physical environment, a classroom structure that is used to engage learners individually or in groups in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities.

Curriculum and Planning. Conceptually, encompasses teachers' capability to interpret curriculum content into learning behavior that are applicable to learners and based on the philosophy of efficient teaching and learning (Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers 2017). In operational sense, it is the designed, managed and implemented sequenced instruction and learning development of teachers to meet curriculum necessities and varied teaching contexts.

Assessment and Reporting. Conceptually, it is a process associated with a variety of assessment tools and strategies used by teachers in monitoring, evaluating, documenting, and reporting learning needs, progress and achievement (Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers 2017). Operationally, it refers to the designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies of the teachers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Training Needs of Teachers

Teachers play a crucial role in nation building. Throughout excellence teachers, the Philippines be able to build up holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st century skills, and able to push the country to improvement and advancement. This is in consonance with the division of Education prophecy of producing: "Filipinos who fervently worship their country and whose values and competencies allow them to appreciate their full imminent and bring expressively to structure the nation" (DepEd Order No. 36, s. 2013).

It was clearly indicated in the Code of Ethics for Qualified Teachers (1997) that a particular educator is an uncovered proficient who takes pride and notoriety with high self-esteem and also specialized and proficient skill. S/he holds fast to

watch and practice an arrangement of moral and good standards, measures, and qualities. In order to develop this, an educator who is a sharp onlooker of this performance sought to have a normal state of instructional capability. When all is said and done, instructors must not be at all inactive of the instructional abilities that they should possess in order to guarantee improvement and quality training on the understudies' part.

According to Guevara and Nuiqui (2015), the informative allotment requires training programs and activities that would well the roles of the instructors. The responsibilities of learning have misused thoroughly as countries change their educational structure to organize students to function in today's world of rapid technological alter and globalization.

Certified education is the strategy used by schools and school districts to make sure that teachers persist to build up their awareness and practices in their teaching vocation. (Mizell,2012).In accumulation, the most efficient professional growth engages team of teachers to focus on the requirements of their pupils. Teachers' commitment in successful professional expansion and in-service trainings increases pupil accomplishment.

The most regarded calling on the planet is educator. S/he is a model and is intentionally imitated. As indicated by Panda and Mohanty (2012), as cited by Askandar, Kadlong and Usop(2013), the instructor is the core of any training framework. In point, teachers are the benefit of a country. Educators create execution style qualities to their methods for identifying with the world, perceptually and also intellectually. Likewise, educator's uplifting state of mind towards instructing and higher goal level decides his/her positive impression of the situations. It is all around perceived that educators' instructional execution assumes a key part in understudies' learning and scholarly accomplishment.

The Philippine Government has constantly pursued teacher excellence reforms through a quantity of initiatives. As a framework of teacher quality, the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) was institutionalized through Commission on Higher Educat (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 52, s. 2007 and DepED Order No. 32, s. 2009. It emerged as part of the accomplishment of the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA), and was facilitated by illustration on the education considerations of projects, such as the essential teaching assistance for Mindanao, the intensification performance of Visayas Education project and the Third Elementary Education Project (TEEP). The K to 12 Reform (R.A. 10533) in 2013 has distorted the scenery of teacher eminence necessities in the Philippines. The reorganization procedure warrants an corresponding supportive focus on teacher superiority – high quality teachers who are appropriately equipped and ready to presume the roles and functions of a K to 12 teachers. On the studies conducted regarding with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) Groh (2017) concluded that among the factors that ensure the quality of education and quality of human property for the improvement of a nation, the quality of its teachers has been measured as a key aspect that plays a important role.

In the Philippine arrangement of training, there are elements that offer trouble to the attainment of goals. The issues of insufficiently prepared educators, absence of bolster either from the administration or from private division, absence of strong arranging, and absence of follow-up of result all add to the trouble (Nem Singh and Padilla, 2012).

One of the goals of today's pre-service and in-service training of teachers is to promote teacher's competencies. Rendering to the Department of Education, it is a big factor in the hypothetical accomplishment of the scholars. Included beneath instructor competencies are coaching effectiveness, specialized appreciation and recognition, membership and contribution in proficient organizations, academic abilities and creative constructiveness, and university and community provision (Manual of Regulation for Private Schools, 2012).

The SEAMEO INNOTECH Regional Education Project Series 2009 (SIREP 2009) looked into a study which investigated the ebb and flow sets of showing capabilities in Southeast Asian nations. It explored how Southeast Asian nations created instructing principles to accomplish quality training. The venture up to this point gave a scene of showing abilities all through the locale. The goal is to help the other part states in benchmarking and building up their own particular showing competency gauges. Their review investigated the significant qualities that characterize a "capable educator" in Southeast Asia. Four properties were flowed for approval of Southeast Asian nations in a SEAMEO INNOTECH overview. The four ascribes identified were educational aptitudes, understudy execution evaluation abilities, classroom administration aptitudes, and proficient improvement abilities.

Furthermore, Non (2012) conducted a study about Teachers' Instructional Competencies and School Effectiveness of the Selected Schools in General Santos City. She found out that the teachers are often methodological, motivational, and

material utilization competent. She recommends that for teachers to become instructionally competent the school should enforce rules and regulations that are clear, fair and well-understood. The training needs of teachers which are given focus in this study are the content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning and assessment and reporting.

In the studies of Madrigal and Roberto (2018), the findings exposed that the level of education standards capability and presentation of basic education teachers as assessed by the principals and teachers themselves were proficient and satisfactory, correspondingly. In addition, the conclusion further showed no important distinction in both the teaching standards competence and performance when the teachers were grouped according to sex, educational accomplishment, marital status, and status of employment. On the other hand, the overall findings revealed that there is a significant association among the level of teaching standards aptitude and performance.

Unay (2019) conducted a study on Secondary School Teachers' Training Needs Assessment in Mondragon Northern Samar: Basis for conservatory agenda of the College of Science, University of Eastern Philippines. In her study, the following are the recommendations as needs in the development of the Extension program of the College of Science: ICT skills for teaching, student discipline and behavior problems, student counseling, content and performance standards in subject field/s, knowledge and understanding of main subject field/s, school management and administration, classroom management, student assessment practices and teaching in a multicultural setting, knowledge and understanding of instructional practices in subject field/s and teaching students with special learning needs.

Lasaten (2016) conducted a study on Assessment Methods, Problems and Training Needs of Public High School Teachers in English. Based from the conclusions drawn in his study, he recommended that the public high school teachers in English from the three schools division of Ilocos Norte have to attend more seminars and trainings on evaluation so they can extend their awareness of the dissimilar methods and approaches of measurement and be given strategies or mechanisms on how to handle assessment troubles being encountered. Likewise, he recommended that a training addressing the teachers' assessment needs has to be proposed and conducted. In addition, a comparable study has to be administered to further validate the result of the present study.

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Mishra and Koehler (2014) had seen pedagogical content knowledge as that knowledge-base which is concerned with the representation and formulation of concepts, pedagogical practices, and acquaintance of what makes thoughts challenging or easy to learn, and awareness of learners' prior awareness. They further added that pedagogical content knowledge as that knowledge is that which involves knowledge of teaching strategies that incorporate appropriate conceptual representations in order to address learner difficulties and misconceptions and to foster meaningful understanding.

Kwong, Joseph, Erick and Khoh (2013) mentioned that educational substance information (Pedagogical Content Knowledge) frames, a one of a kind and unmistakable learning area of educator comprehension. Pedagogical Content Knowledge underscores the way in which educators relate their topic information (what they think about what they instruct) to their academic information (what they think about educating, how their learners' learn and the learners' originations) and how topic information is a piece of the procedure of educational thinking. It additionally grasps an insightful of what makes the information of clear discernments simple or troublesome, the originations and predispositions that understudies of various ages and foundations convey with them to the learning condition. Accordingly, academic substance learning (Pedagogical Content Knowledge) is seen as that trademark mindfulness territory of showing that recognizes the master instructor in a branch of knowledge from the subject matter.

According to Groh (2017) recommended that besides incentives for teachers, investment in developing educational institutions, teacher training, a system of standards for teaching profession, or teachers' competencies standards, needs to be developed. In fact he stated that, teachers' competencies standards have been developed and completed in many countries nowadays.

Furthermore, Turnuklu and Yesildere (2017) worked according to a framework that could be used to assess the teachers' abilities to incorporate technological devices in teaching. They also emphasized the need for teachers to have a good understanding of the topics that they intend to teach, in order for them to select an appropriate technological device that

could be used in teaching. The inclusion of subject matter knowledge as part of the framework used for this study is thus further justified by these findings.

In addition, in the study conducted by Suarez (2017) also pointed out that Learning Action Cell or LAC which is also called quality learning circle for teachers is an accomplishment being facilitated in school for teachers' specialized perfection to increase their teaching skills and performance of the students surrounded by the four corners of the classroom.

The findings of Yson (2017) revealed that the quality of a nation's education and human resources depend much on its teaching workforce. thus, working out a teacher with sufficient competencies is playing a serious role for country's improvement. Teacher's proficient competencies and teacher's professional progress contribute a lot.

According to Vermunt (2014), high excellence educator knowledge influences student-learning product as a result. Teachers must experience cognitive and meta cognitive learning processes in direct to attain learning outcome in the form of changed believes about their practice or, even better, change in behaviour. These processes are cognitive thoughts actions that are used to practice learning content, for example classroom administration. Teacher outcomes in terms of enhanced knowledge and skills in a field of classroom management influence student learning environment and student learning outcome because of changed student learning processes.

On the other hand, Pianta and colleagues (2012), teachers should concentrate on emotional support, classroom organization and instructional support aspects of classroom interaction among teacher and students. To be capable to do that, it requires that the teacher, possesses a positive set of information and skills to comprehend how these three domains work, what dissimilarity they can make for a teacher in the classroom and why they are so significant. It is research confirmed knowledge that classroom communication is a tool for any teacher, which will sustain him/her in any classroom condition.

Quadri (2014) as cited by Navarro (2014) corroborates that a good teacher must be knowledgeable enough in his area of specialization. He should recognize which to teach, when to teach and how to teach. The magnitude and excellence of the teacher's awareness will give the teacher plenty substantial and assurance to teach successfully.

As indicated by Muijs and Reynolds (2012) as cited by Mariano (2013) claim that how a teacher teaches becomes a vital key in promoting effective teaching and learning to the students. The researchers acquired curiosity in the training of how the teachers' capabilities affect the scholarship of the students whom they are teaching. Therefore, the teachers themselves are given the obligation to mold students into learned, competent, responsible and moral citizens of the country which is aligned with the aim of every educational institution that is to produce competent and excellent graduates.

Unmistakably, academic abilities are a considerable segment of showing competency in the Southeast Asian locale. This is in support to the discoveries of Brunett (2012) that each youngster needs to be taught twenty-first century abilities to prevail with regards to learning and life. Educator instruction pioneers need to deliberately consider actualizing twenty-first century academic abilities into learning and work long haul to make an instructive framework that better readies today's understudies for tomorrow's working environment.

On the study conducted by Bada (2016) emphasized that a teacher who have the content knowledge and knows how to apply it across the curriculum displays extensive knowledge of the important concepts in the discipline and how these relate both to one another and to other disciplines.. The results of the study of Ozden (2018) emphasized that content knowledge and application skills of a teacher had positive influence on learning while it improves effective teaching practice.

On the other hand, teachers having inaccurate and inadequate knowledge might transfer their own misconceptions to their students (Hashweh, 2016) and in this way add to students' conceptual difficulties (Even, 2017). Kaya (2018) showed that there was a momentous interrelationship among the subject matter and pedagogical information of the teachers. In the same way, several researchers such as Halim and Meerah (2012), Van Driel, De Jong and Verloop (2016) concluded that content knowledge had manipulate on pedagogical content knowledge. However, content knowledge had no result on pedagogical content knowledge according to Mapolelo (2015).

The Theory of Constructivism represents one of the big ideas in education (Bada, 2016). It is the primary speculation in teaching and learning. It was the anchor of this study since its purpose was not to set standards but to look into possible areas for the development of teachers based on the given standards aided by their learning experiences (Petalla & Madrigal, 2017). Primarily, educational reforms aimed for all students to succeed (Bada, 2016). In the light of these reforms, the

students must be the center of education. Gilis, et al. (2018) pointed out that constructivism has shifted in pedagogy from teacher-focused to student-focused. This is the most important contribution of constructivism in education (Bada, 2016).

Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Teachers play a fundamental role in the cognitive and social-emotional development of the children by giving them the opportunity to learn. Operative classroom administration sets the period for this scholarship. Without it, classrooms are disorganized and chaotic, and very little academic learning can happen (Elias & Schwab, 2013). Further, Singh (2015) emphasized in his study that in order to meet the needs of all students and design programs that are responsive to the intellectual strengths and personal interests of students, teachers must have the competencies and must explore alternatives to traditional instruction.

With modern-day classrooms flatteringly increasingly diverse, educational establishment, teachers and school administrators are looking to teaching and learning strategies that furnish for a diversity of learning profiles. As what the Department of Education of the Australian Government (2018) said, inclusive education means that all students are able to attend and are welcomed by their neighborhood school in age-appropriate, standard classrooms and are supported to learn, contribute and play a part in all aspects of school days. Inclusive education is about how we develop and design our schools, classrooms and activities so that all students learn and participate together so therefore, teachers should have good competencies in handling and teaching learners with varied behavior, gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences.

The study of Nem Singh and Padilla (2013) raised five major concerns in classroom management: individual concerns; harnessing self-control; encouragement; reaching-out to students and disciplining students' behavior, while the study of Martin and Sass (2012) revealed that classroom administration involves an umbrella of definitions that incorporate learning associations, learning, and the conduct of understudies.

Further, Walker (2014) expressed that the best instructors don't just show content; they educate individuals. To effectively educate their understudies, the educators prerequisite to engagement agent execution organization approaches, actualize powerful instructional methodologies, and build up solid educational modules. Notwithstanding his/her dealing with the guidelines in the classroom, an educator's most noteworthy test is likewise dealing with the conduct of the understudies in the classroom in light of how it can influence direction, learning, and accomplishment. Since the guidelines going with the government law NCLB (No Child Left Behind), the CCRPI (College and Career Ready Performance Index), and accomplishment based projects, for example, Race to the Top, educators are worried about rebuffing understudies in ways that will expel them from the standard classroom setting.

In addition, teachers play a fundamental role in the cognitive and social-emotional development of the children by giving them the opportunity to learn. Operative classroom administration sets the period for this scholarship. Without it, classrooms are disorganized and chaotic, and very little academic learning can happen (Elias & Schwab, 2016).

To many, the term classroom management is educational terminology for obedience. This should not be the case. Discipline is but only one aspect of classroom management as it implies the exercise of control by the teacher over the pupils' actions and behavior to establish order in the classroom. Nevertheless, classroom management is the teacher's ability to create that conducive, positive learning climate within the classroom so as to ensure that all pupils would be enthusiastically involved in learning and, consequently, there would be no place for any pupil misbehavior Goh (2015).

One characteristic trait of an effective teacher is the ability to manage resources to facilitate learning. Management is an integral part of the leader's role in the learning environment. The teachers are accountable for supervision their own classrooms. In the framework of learning to manage would mean to direct, guide, control and cope with. Managing the classroom is part of a teachers' instructional task (Salandron, 2012).

Riemers (2013) emphasizes that good teaching methods have a significant positive impact on how and what students learn. With this, Agayi (2015) evaluates the appropriateness of instructional practices of teachers to meet their own needs and interests such as their unique ways of teaching and classroom management styles. In helping students to understand diverse perspectives and texts and to develop the ability to communicate ideas, the most effective teachers use knowledge about students' backgrounds and cognitive development to inform their choices of instructional strategies and materials. The instructional design must provide challenging and varied opportunities for students to develop as readers, writers, and

thinkers. The focus is on students' responses to texts as they make connections, explore themes, and expand their knowledge of self and the world. The role of the teacher is to support students as they actively construct meaning and build collective and individual understanding.

Indeed, classroom assessment includes a wide array of tasks from constructing tests and performance measures, to grading, interpreting test scores, communicating test results, and using assessment results in making decisions. It is then imperative for teachers to know the strengths and weaknesses of each of the assessment methods used. They should choose right formats to assess student achievements (Branda, 2013). Tests items should manifest content validity (Fremwe, 2012). They should also be geared towards developing higher-order thinking skills among students. In performance assessment, reliability and validity can be improved through the use of measurable, observable and clearly defined performance standards (Phillips, 2014) descriptive scoring rubrics, varied samples of behaviors evaluated by several judges, and recording results during assessment (Thompson, 2014). Improving and revising teacher-made tests based on item analysis is also necessary. Assessment, therefore, involves review of evidence of learning such as journal entries, written work, portfolios, skill demonstrations, and performance in learning activities, test results and rubrics ratings which cover a period of time and should reveal the progress of students in competencies (Zang, 2012).

Furthermore, Doyle (2012) emphasized that classroom management is an ability would which include the teacher's skills in delivering interesting lessons, in organizing and managing smoothly learning activities for individual pupils, groups or the entire class, and in establishing close rapport and understanding with pupils. Classroom management provides the basis for creating this conducive learning atmosphere. To make the class 'tick' this way is no simple task owing to the number of individuals found within a classroom.

Basically, the role of a classroom teacher involves two major interdependent tasks: to establish order and to facilitate learning (Doyle, 2012). A teacher must not only be able to impart knowledge and facilitate learning, but he must be able to create or provide that 6 Teaching and Learning congenial environment for such learning to take effect. It is against this background that the current research into classroom practices and teacher behaviors arouses much enthusiasm and attracts financial support. (Jones 2012).

In the study of Sadik and Akbulut (2015), they found out that significant relations were there between classroom management skills and some variables such as gender, age, professional experience, classroom management courses/seminars taken before, reading classroom management books, pedagogical background, types of schools. The skills that must be improved most are collaboration with administration, parents and counseling service foundation for the problems that teachers cannot overcome; using educational equipment in correlation with the course content; guiding students for more productive activities rather than taking the problematic behaviors under control.

It was revealed in the study conducted by Jones (2016) on inclusive education, he concluded that teaching inclusively equates creating a learning environment where students, irrespective of their background can maximize the potential for their own learning and the learning of others.

It is universally recognized that teacher is a backbone of any educational system because knowledge is transferred from the teachers to the taught. Every country is giving prime importance to the quality of teachers and national policies have been influenced by the growing realization that teachers have a key role to play in determining the quality of output of educational institutions (Gov't. of Pakistan, 2014). Secret of quality education lies in the quality of teachers. Cochran (2006) artistically described the same idea, "It is a universal fact that quality of students depends upon the quality of teachers either highly qualified or have high professional development."

In addition, Linways (2017) emphasized in his study that the mark of a great teacher is the ability to infer what their students need. The education should ultimately be student centric. Along the curriculum till the end, a teacher must consistently take feedback and perform course-correction in their plan. Linways (2017) gained support from the Donsi (2018) as his study stated that no matter how good a plan is, there can always be room for unexpected twists and turns in your way.

It was revealed in the study conducted by Cuangco (2011) that teaching-practices, which the teacher applies, have a vital role in the student-learning. This training purposes to classify the best performance of English teachers for the elementary grades in Angeles Elementary School. In the process of identifying those practices, they enumerated the ways the English

teachers deliver their lessons like teaching style, subject expertise, teaching environment, community involvement, and professional development.

Furthermore, Kyikci (2012) pointed out that majority of disciplinary incidents that take place in the classroom originate from the insufficiency of teachers' classroom management skills. His study aimed to assess the effect of elementary school teachers' classroom management skills on the discipline behavior of students.

He also added that a significant relation between the dimensions regarding classroom management skills of the teachers and disciplinary behavior of the students was observed. It was seen that there was a positive relation between all the dimensions of students' disciplinary behavior and teachers' skills and core competencies in classroom management.

Curriculum and Planning

In his findings, Smorn (2017) stated that from theory to practice, the developments of the curriculum, textbooks, teaching conditions, etc. are hard to promote the efficiency, or even useless, if the quality of teachers is weak or is not taken into account. Thus, (Dehk, 2017) supported that for many countries around the world, teachers and teacher quality should appear in the education development strategies with great attention and to be considered as the key factor for the success of education and country development.

On the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), the studies of (Dizon, San Pedro, et.al, 2018) concluded that RPMS provides policies, specific mechanisms, criteria and processes for the performance target setting, monitoring, evaluation and development planning for the ratees. However, majority of the raters fail to discuss those with the ratees as well as how the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form is being prepared.

In the findings conducted by Padilla 2018, it concluded that RPMS focuses on measures of performance vis-à-vis the targeted milestones. It also provides a credible and verifiable basis for assessing the organizational outcomes and the collective performance of the government employees.

Along the way, the findings of Pascual (2018) added that the RPMS is effective when it comes to identifying the ratees' competencies as they are monitored to effectively plan the interventions needed for behavioral and professional development. However, the raters just lack the sufficient knowledge on what proper developmental intervention to employ for the ratees.

The Department of Education (DepEd) (2016) is committed to provide the members of its organization with opportunities to link their individual achievements and make a meaningful contribution to the attainment of the institution's Vision and Mission. It also promotes individual and team growth, participation and commitment. Lastly, it grows professionally and personally.

Kartanaka (2012) added that as the teachers possess competencies in planning and managing learning, this expects teachers to make arrangements and develop an orderly structure to combine all elements in classroom processes into a unified whole. Well organizing is closely associated with systematic planning.

Muhammad (2018) empirical study aimed at finding out the factors influencing use of ICT to make teaching learning effective in higher institutions of learning and identifying the innovations that ICT has brought into the teaching-learning process, particularly in higher institutions of learning. A survey was employed in order to empirically investigate the study

In connection with this, a multiple-case-study research methodology was conducted by Sangra and Sanmamed (2018). From a previous exploratory research, four different types of schools were determined.

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (2017) defines teacher quality in the Philippines. The standards describe the expectations of teachers' increasing levels of knowledge, practice and professional engagement. At the same time, the standards allow for teachers' growing understanding, applied with increasing sophistication across a broader and more complex range of teaching/learning situations.

According to Briones (2017) pointed out that the PPST will be the basis for all learning and development programs for teachers to ensure that they are properly equipped to effectively implement the K to 12. The PPST targets to produce better teachers in the country by improving their qualifications skills and by increasing their levels of knowledge, practice and professional engagement.

PPST Manual (2017) states teacher professional development happens in a continuum from beginning to exemplary practice. Anchored on the principle of lifelong learning, the set of professional standards for teachers recognizes the significance of a standards framework that articulates developmental progression as teachers develop, refine their practice and respond to the complexities of educational reforms.

On the studies conducted regarding with the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC), the findings of Suarez (2017) revealed that the teaching ability of the teachers has improved after the conduct of SLAC in terms of content and strategy in all subjects and it was validated during the observation of classes before and after the conduct of SLAC by instructional supervisors. There was a significant difference on the teaching ability of the teachers before and after the conduct of SLAC.

According to Luistro (2016), through this policy, the DepEd fully encourages the continuing professional growth of its teaching personnel based on the policy of lifelong learning and DepEd's commitment to the development of teachers' potential aimed towards their success in the profession. Development of teachers' potential can be realized through the school-based Learning Action Cell, which primarily functions as professional learning communities for teachers that will help them improve practice and learner achievement.

DepEd Order No. 18, s.2014 stated that at the end of the Second Quarter, a midterm break should be observed to evaluate individual teachers and their collective achievement, as well as to conduct the In-service Training (INSET) activities in support of continuing professional development.

A School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) is a group of teachers who engage in collaborative learning sessions to solve shared difficulties encountered in the school facilitated by the school head or a designated SLAC Leader. Learning Action Cells will become the school-based communities of practice that are positive, caring, and safe spaces.

DepEd (2017) envisions that these LAC Sessions will serve as a school-based continuing professional development strategy for the improvement of teaching and learning. As such, in the study of Cabral (2019) it aimed to assess the impact of conducting LAC sessions on teachers' professional development in schools. In his findings, he stated that there is effect on their (teachers) professional development, and there were also problems encountered in participating to it. As Lewis (2002) added, SLAC is very crucial and beneficial for professional development is the key to educational improvement.

Siddiqui (2010) has directed his learning about an investigation of instructor's abilities by showing researches for school viability and welfare the school. Significant discoveries of his review showed that however the greater part of the educators know about norms of instructing for school adequacy to some degree yet they are not executing these measures in their classrooms. Additionally, larger parts of the educators are not utilizing assessment procedures appropriately. The educators, be that as it may, concurred with two noteworthy qualities of the instructor training for school viability i.e. content learning and instructive capabilities. The fundamental ramifications of the preparation is to move from address worldview to community oriented, intelligent and popularity based instruction style and advance coaching and also checking instructor showing program for general school adequacy.

Assessment and Reporting

Student performance assessment is inescapable in schools, yet just a couple of instructive experts have substantive capabilities to embrace learner evaluation. Educators must have the capacities to utilized changed states of mind and gadgets. It is critical that there should be an input to the part of the instructor with respect to how much the previously mentioned learning results have been accomplished. This remark allows the instructor to make noteworthy varieties in education and training frameworks. Through this criticism procedure, educators start to understand that all techniques for learning are not similarly viable. The aptitude of the educator to evaluate students' performance can direct imperative instructional changes (Research Studies Unit, SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2009).

On the other hand, Carter & Nunan (2013) mentioned that classroom appraisal and assessment under the dynamic administration of educators can likewise fill essential expert advancement needs since the data coming about because of such assessments furnishes instructors with profitable criticism about their instructional viability that they can use to create and enhance their expert abilities.

Goodrum, Hackling & Rennie (2014) expressed that, in a perfect world, evaluation on learning, gives criticism about understudy advance, forms fearlessness and confidence, and creates abilities in assessment. Also, they contend that viable learning happens when correspondence exists between education, assessment, and results. In this way, because of its nearby connection with guideline and learning results, appraisal has a key part in learning.

As indicated by Moe (2012), instructors' capacities to adequately apply evaluation forms into their educating are imperative. The educated choices this permits can give instructors the learning that they should have the capacity to effectively instruct the understudies in their classroom. Instructors that don't comprehend the evaluation procedure will basically be traveling through the educating and learning process indiscriminately, and conceivably, giving more mischief to the understudies than doing great. Instructors enter the calling to work with understudies and enable them to develop socially, inwardly, and scholastically. In any case, to have the capacity to do that, these youthful educators must enter their vocations with enough preparation and sufficient knowledge and skills that will enable them to succeed. It is the officeholder who sets up training projects for these educators to comprehend the whole showing procedure, and how the diverse segments connect and sustain each other. An instructor should be solid in their comprehension of substance, instructional method, understudies' social and enthusiastic needs, and appraisals and not in disconnection.

According to Kasmie (2013), the need for in-service training in schools is getting more attention for teachers to equip with new knowledge and skills for them to face new challenges and reformation in education. In-service training can enhance the professionalism of teachers who can contribute to the organisation to achieve its goals. In-service training is a professional and personal educational activity for teachers to improve their efficiency, ability, knowledge and motivation in their professional work. In-service training offers one of the most promising roads to the improvement of instruction. It includes goal and content, the training process and the context. In-service training is the totality of educational and personal experiences that contribute toward an individual being more competent and satisfied in an assigned professional role. The primary purpose of in-service training is to enable teachers to acquire new understanding and instructional skills. It focuses on creating learning environments which enable teachers to develop their effectiveness in the classroom. In this aspect, in-service training for teachers is the driving force behind much change that has occurred in the area of teaching and learning. It is vital that teachers keep up to date on the most current concepts, thinking and research in their field and also promote professional growth among teachers in order to promote excellent and effective teaching and learning environment for students.

In the study conducted by Smith (2017) confirmed that the learning and development programs provided for the professional teachers and the process of complying the CPD help them (teachers) manage their own professional and teaching development on an ongoing basis as this was supported by Bream (2017) who concluded that learning and development systems which are inclined with the present mandates and programs of the country could produce quality and effective professional teachers.

Eberl (2015) emphasized that assessments should reveal how well students have learned what we want them to learn while instruction ensures that they learn it. For this to occur, teachers must possess the competencies in selecting, organizing, utilizing and assessing strategies to achieve greater teaching and learning performances. In addition, assessments, learning objectives, and instructional strategies need to be closely aligned so that they reinforce one another.

Furthermore Dadaso (2017) concluded that compliance with CPD through appropriate L and D provides an overview of teachers' professional development to date, reminds them of their achievements and how far they have progressed, directs their career and helps them keep eyes on their goals, uncovers gaps in their skills and capabilities.

Moreover, Millan (2017) supported this by stating that L and D and CPD consciousness opens up further development needs of professional teachers, provides examples and scenarios for a CV or interview, demonstrates professional standing to clients and employer and helps teachers with their development or a possible career change.

Barandon and Atian (2016) put emphasis on how assessment plays a crucial role in the delivery of quality education. In the triad of education, assessment is considered one of the key areas aside from curriculum and instruction; thus, educators need to give premium to classroom assessment techniques. Their descriptive study determined the level of awareness and extent of competencies in the utilization of classroom assessment techniques by the teachers. Over-all, it is concluded that the higher the level of awareness and competencies of the faculty, the higher is their extent of utilization of classroom

assessment techniques. Among the proposed measures to enhance utilization of classroom assessment technique are training in classroom assessment by external experts, intensive follow-up activity after the training, other in-service trainings such as SLAC sessions and classroom observation.

In the comprehensive review of teachers' competencies in utilizing assessment methods, Palomba and Banta (2016) further described assessment as a process that focuses on student learning. Teachers' higher competencies in the utilization of assessment strategies equate higher learning achievements. Such has been supported by Bantas (2017) who stated that teachers with greater knowledge and skills in assessment help achieve good academic standing of the learners.

When schools and community organizations work together to support learning, everyone benefits. Partnerships can serve to strengthen, support, and even transform individual partners, resulting in improved program quality, more efficient use of resources, and better alignment of goals and curricula (Harvard Family Research Project, 2012).

Similarly, Magalso (2017) also stated that L and D with CPD compliance helps teachers review and reflect on their any learning experiences over the previous year or over the past three months, write thoughts down about what they learned, what insights it gave you and what they might have done differently which includes learning from colleagues or shared learning from networking, reading about new technologies, new methods of working, legislative changes, shadowing or assisting an experienced colleague, insights and learning points from coaching and mentoring, reflections and insights and learning points from taking on a new responsibility. Harfitt (2018) viewed learning as a social and cultural process. The premise of this paper is that teachers' developing expertise should not only reside in the knowledge domains typically established by universities and schools. With this, Themes (2018) added that teachers with good competencies when it comes to community linkages promote good learning and developed school community.

Furthermore, Jacob and Lefgren (2016) set up a positive connection between a primary's evaluation of how powerful an educator is at raising learners' accomplishment and that instructor's achievement in doing as such as exact by the esteem included approach. The above review proposes that chairman's appraising may likewise be one of a far reaching assessment framework to quantify instructors' viability in private auxiliary schools. In this way, thusly successful educators totally impact the scholarly accomplishment of understudies.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study utilized a cross sectional survey that aims at finding out the prevalence of the outcome of interest (Levin 2014). Cross sectional survey collects data to make inference about a population or interest. It describes as snapshots of the population about which they gathered data.

Cross sectional survey intends to describe the training needs or priority of public elementary school teachers for mentoring and coaching in Malapatan 1 District. Likewise, it was also the basis for the formation of the intervention program towards addressing the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.

The study was conducted in all public elementary schools in Malapatan 1 District, Division of Sarangani Province. This consisted of eight (8) elementary schools namely: Alyeng Elementary School located at Sapu Masla, Malapatan Sarangani Province. Aspang Elementary School also located in the same District in the far flung area. Datu Pangolima Integrated School is located in Sapu Padidu, Malapatan Sarangani Province. Lasang Elementary School, also found in the far flung area of Sapu Masla, Malapatan Sarangani Province. Malapatan Central Elementary School is a central school in the Municipality where in it is the center of the District. Malkahi Elementary School also in the Poblacion of Malapatan located in the far flung area. Mama Nawa Elementary School a school in the District that majority of the population is Islam and Sitio Lanao Elementary School is the farthest school in the District also located in the same District.

The respondents of the study were the one-hundred seventy one (171) public elementary school teachers in Malapatan 1 District. This research covered all public elementary school teachers in Malapatan 1 District since RPMS is being implemented among public school teachers in the country in consonance with the Civil Service Commission's (CSC) Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) through DepEd order no. 21 series of 2015.

The needed data for this study were gathered using a survey questionnaire adapted from Results-Based Performance Management System-Philippine-Professional Standards for Teachers Manual for Teachers and School Heads. The

instrument refers to the training needs of teachers in Malapatan 1 District. Data collected were interpreted using a four-point Likert scale with the following description: 4 Strongly Needed, 3 Much Needed, 2 Less Needed and 1 Not Needed.

Weighted mean was used to treat the gathered data of this study. To describe the training needs of teachers, the following with description will be used. 1.00 - 1.75 Not Needed, 1.76 - 2.50 Less Needed, 2.51 - 3.25 Much Needed, 3.26 – 4.00 Strongly Needed.

Data gathering started with the preparation of letters which sought permission for the conduct of the study. First, letters of request were sent to the School's Division Superintendent of Sarangani Province, Public School District Supervisor and School Heads of the chosen schools asking for permission to conduct the study (refer to Appendix A, B and C). Once permission was given, a suitable approved schedule for the data collection was set. After the instruments were prepared and finalized, and with the approval letters already received from the schools, the school heads of the participating schools were notified via messenger and arranged a suitable schedule for administering the questionnaire online.

On the scheduled date and time, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaires to the respondents online via Google Forms due to the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) outbreak so social distancing as a safety measure was observed in compliance to the mandate of the government. Prior to this, the researcher explained the objective of conducting the study, assuring them that the data collected would be treated with utmost confidentiality. As soon as the respondents have answered all the items in the questionnaire, the researcher collected the instrument automatically via Google Forms, tabulated the results and submitted the same to a statistician for data analysis.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Training Needs Assessment of Public School Teachers in Malapatan 1 District in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning and Assessment and Reporting.

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

As evaluated by the teachers, the need for training in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy was $\bar{x}=3.28$ strongly needed. Teachers want to improve their necessary knowledge across curriculum areas and be familiar with the methodologies and pedagogical approaches.

Malapatan Central Elementary School teachers believed that their most priority is to improve critical contents and topics identified subject areas $\bar{x}=3.31$ strongly needed and Alyeng Elementary School need to be equipped in creating a genuine discussion and provision of broad range of questions and activities, including those of higher-order that challenge learners to analyze their thinking to promote deeper thinking $\bar{x}=3.30$ strongly needed.

Malkahi Elementary School teachers believed that they have much to improve on the application of extensive knowledge of content beyond their specialization $\bar{x}=3.26$ strongly needed and Sitio Lanao Elementary School need to be upgrade in utilization of intra- and interdisciplinary content relationships like peer mentoring focused group discussion with colleagues $\bar{x}=3.27$ strongly needed.

The results of the investigation implied that teacher's' priority for mentoring is to apply their extensive knowledge of content through attending seminars, and trainings, peer mentoring, focused group discussion with colleagues and attending SLAC sessions to developed their intra and interdisciplinary content relationships for their own personal growth and development to enhance learner achievement.

Groh (2017) recommended that besides incentives for teachers, investment in developing educational institutions, teacher training, a system of standards for teaching profession, or teachers' competencies standards, needs to be developed. In fact he stated that teachers' competencies standards have been developed and completed in many countries nowadays. After decades, by professional standards, teachers and educational institutions already have the basement for cultivating and expertise. This is a goal to strive for, a measure for managers and teachers to evaluate and self-evaluate. This also is a significant step forward in education science, in training and retraining of teachers.

The findings of Yson (2017) revealed that the quality of a nation's education and human resources depend much on its teaching workforce. Hence, training a teacher with adequate competencies is playing a critical role for country's development. Teacher's professional competencies and teacher's professional development contribute a lot.

Suarez, 2017 also pointed out that Learning Action Cell or LAC which is also called Quality Learning Circle for Teachers, and Teachers Quality Circle in other schools, is an activity being conducted in school for teachers' professional development to improve their teaching skills and performance of the pupils/students inside the classroom.

Bada (2016) also emphasized that a teacher who has the content knowledge and knows how to apply it across the curriculum displays extensive knowledge of the important concepts in the discipline and how these relate both to one another and to other disciplines. The teacher demonstrates understanding of prerequisite relationships among topics and concepts and understands the link to necessary cognitive structures that ensure student understanding. The teacher's plans and practice reflect familiarity with a wide range of effective pedagogical approaches in the discipline and the ability to anticipate student misconceptions. The results of the study of Ozden (2018) emphasized that content knowledge and application skills of a teacher had a positive influence on learning while it improves effective teaching practice.

Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

The mean results of the evaluation of all teachers in Malapatan 1 District to their training needs in terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners. Data revealed that teachers' training in Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners with the description of much needed $\bar{x}=3.07$.

As evaluated by the teachers, Datu Panglima Elementary School and Lasang Elementary School teachers, they put so much regard to improve and learn more about the utilization of proactive classroom structure management and practices to support flexible movement of learners in all learning activities $\bar{x}=3.25$ Much Needed and using of differentiated strategies that motivate and engage group of learners at their cognitive levels management of classroom structure $\bar{x}=3.25$ much needed.

On the other hand, Aspang Elementary School and Sitio Lanao Elementary School they see least important for training in the organization of learners behaviour constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments $\bar{x}=2.78$ much needed and managing of classroom structure and activities specifically in Developing 21st Century Classroom Management Skills and Crafting a Functional Classroom Management Plan (CMP) $\bar{x}=2.78$ much needed.

The result of the investigation revealed that public elementary school teachers in Malapatan District 1 want to enhance skills in the utilization of hands-on classroom structure management and practices that engages learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities that support flexible movement of learners in all learning activities in the management of classroom structure.

This agrees with the idea of Goh (2015) and Doyle (2012). According to these researchers, classroom management is the teacher's ability which includes the teacher's skills in delivering interesting lessons, in organizing and managing smoothly learning activities for individual pupils, groups or the entire class in creating a conducive, positive learning climate within the classroom so as to ensure that all pupils would be enthusiastically involved in learning. Consequently, there would be no place for any pupil misbehavior. Classroom management structure provides the basis for creating this conducive learning atmosphere. To make the class 'tick' this way is no simple task owing to the number of individuals found within a classroom.

Furthermore, Kyikci (2012) pointed out that majority of disciplinary incidents that take place in the classroom originate from the insufficiency of teachers' classroom management skills. His study aimed to assess the effect of elementary school teachers' classroom management skills on the discipline behavior of students.

He also added that a significant relation between the dimensions regarding classroom management skills of the teachers and disciplinary behavior of the students was observed. It was seen that there was a positive relation between all the dimensions of students' disciplinary behavior and teachers' skills and core competencies in classroom management.

Curriculum and Planning

This study identified that the need for training of all teachers in Malapatan 1 District in terms of Curriculum and Planning was $\bar{x}=3.20$ with the description of much needed.

Teachers in Alyeng Elementary School put so much concern to improve on the selection, development, organization and the use of appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT, to address learning goals $\bar{x}=3.34$ strongly needed.

On the other hand Aspang Elementary School teachers see least important to develop more in the teaching-Learning resources including ICT (i.e. Technology-Enhanced Learning Approaches, Multi-media Based Instruction, etc.) $\bar{x}=3.23$ much needed. Mama Nawa Elementary School teachers least important for training and development in the preparation of sequence of activities purposefully scaffold learners toward achieving the lesson's objectives. $\bar{x}=3.12$ much needed and Sitio Lanao Elementary School also have least priority in connecting of outcomes to previous and future learning. Transitions between activities are smooth $\bar{x}=3.11$ much needed.

The results of the investigation implied that public elementary school teachers in Malapatan 1 District want to develop their teaching skills, learning resources including ICT and communicate learning goals to support learner participation, understanding and achievement.

The effectiveness of professional development depends on how carefully educators conceive, plan and implement it. Planning is important. No matter if it's for your classroom, going to a supermarket, or buying a car. In education, a well-worked out course/lesson plan will act as a core of the teaching-learning process. It answers all the necessary questions and provides sufficient support to the teacher so that the teaching becomes smooth and easy (Mizell, 2012).

Kartanaka (2012) added that as the teachers possess competencies in planning and managing learning, this expects teachers to make arrangements and develop an orderly structure to combine all elements in classroom processes into a unified whole. Well organizing is closely associated with systematic planning. Further, planning is concerned with identification of appropriate activities, organizing is concerned with making arrangements and structuring the classroom to implement classroom activities. The role of the teacher as an organizer is to link planning with all other roles of communicating, motivating and controlling. Planning is one of the important attributes of educational management. To achieve the aims and objectives of education, effective planning with organizing, staffing, directing and controlling are required.

Muhammad (2018) empirical study aimed at finding out the factors influencing use of ICT to make teaching learning effective in higher institutions of learning and identifying the innovations that ICT has brought into the teaching-learning process, particularly in higher institutions of learning. A survey was employed in order to empirically investigate the study. The findings of this study revealed that teaching staff and administrators had a strong desire to have competencies to integrate ICT into the teaching-learning processes. The innovations that ICT has brought in the teaching-learning process include: E-learning, e-communication, quick access to information, online student registration, online advertisement, reduced burden of keeping hardcopy, networking with resourceful persons, etc. However, the presence of all these factors increased the chance of excellent integration of ICT in teaching-learning process. Therefore, the training of teaching staff in the pedagogical issues and administrators in administration issues should be increased if teachers and administrators are to be convinced of the value of using ICT in their teaching-learning process and administration (Muhammad, 2018).

In connection with this, a multiple-case-study research methodology was conducted by Sangra and Sanmamed (2018). From a previous exploratory research, four different types of schools were determined.

Assessment and Reporting

The evaluation of teachers in all schools in Malapatan 1 District about their training needs in terms of Assessment and Reporting. As assessed by the teachers, their need for training in Assessment and Reporting was $\bar{x}=3.19$ with the description of much needed.

Data revealed that teachers in Mama Nawa Elementary School and Sitio Lanao Elementary School that the monitoring and evaluating learner progress and achievement using learning attainment data $\bar{x}=3.21$ much needed, communicating promptly and clearly the learners' need, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents and guardians $\bar{x}=3.21$ much needed, appeared to be the top most priorities for mentoring in Assessment and Reporting of public elementary school teachers in Malapatan 1 District.

Lasang Elementary School teachers also put want to improve on the use of assessment strategies which are embedded as an integral part of the lesson that is aligned with the intended instructional or consistent with the content standards, developing

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (79-98), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Community Linkages, Professional Engagement and using of assessment strategies which engage my learners in assessment criteria to self-monitor and reflect on their own progress $\bar{x}=3.11$ much needed.

The results of the investigation infer that teachers wanted to learn more about the use and utilization of different assessment strategies consistent with the curriculum requirements and standards and to enhance prompt communication with stakeholders, including parents and guardians.

Eberl (2015) emphasized that assessments should reveal how well students have learned what we want them to learn while instruction ensures that they learn it. For this to occur, teachers must possess the competencies in selecting, organizing, utilizing and assessing strategies to achieve greater teaching and learning performances. In addition, assessments, learning objectives, and instructional strategies need to be closely aligned so that they reinforce one another.

Barandon and Atian (2016) put emphasis on how assessment plays a crucial role in the delivery of quality education. In the triad of education, assessment is considered one of the key areas aside from curriculum and instruction. In the comprehensive review of teachers' competencies in utilizing assessment methods, Palomba and Banta (2016) further described assessment as a process that focuses on student learning. Teachers' higher competencies in the utilization of assessment strategies equate higher learning achievements. Such has been supported by Bantas (2017) who stated that teachers with greater knowledge and skills in assessment help achieve good academic standing of the learners.

Harfitt (2018) viewed learning as a social and cultural process. The premise of this paper is that teachers' developing expertise should not only reside in the knowledge domains typically established by universities and schools. In the study conducted by Smith (2017) confirmed that the learning and development programs provided for the professional teachers and the process of complying the CPD help them (teachers) manage their own professional and teaching development on an ongoing basis as this was supported by Bream (2017) who concluded that learning and development systems which are inclined with the present mandates and programs of the country could produce quality and effective professional teachers.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were hereby given:

1. District head should monitor his/her teachers in developing their extensive knowledge of content through attending seminars, trainings, peer mentoring, focused group discussion with colleagues and attending SLAC sessions to develop their professional growth and development.
2. Teachers should be able to integrate well-connected teaching strategies that promote individual and group learners' critical literacy and/or critical numeracy skills like attending trainings on differentiated instructions.
3. Teachers should manage routinization of activities to enhance learners' literacy and numeracy skills in all aspects of the lesson like attending trainings on literacy and numeracy teaching strategies and techniques.
4. Teachers should enhance integration on well-connected teaching strategies that promote individual and group learners' critical literacy and/or critical numeracy skills like attending trainings on differentiated instructions.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the study on Training Needs Assessment of Public School Teachers in Malapatan 1 District, it was found out that in content knowledge and pedagogy was strongly needed while in the three domains: Learning environment and diversity; Curriculum and planning and Assessment and reporting were much needed.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher would like to express his heartfelt gratitude to the following individuals who are responsible for the success of this study. To Dr. Cornillio R. Rollo, his adviser, for the untiring guidance, assistance, suggestions, and expertise in making this research work possible. To the Panel Examiners headed by Dr. Geraldine G. Rodriquez, Vice President for the academic affairs, Dr. Johny B. Bantulo, Dr. Analiza Amada and Dr. Diendo, whose help and brilliant ideas contributed to the completion of research undertaking; To Mr. Gildo G. Mosqueda, the Schools Division Superintendent of Sarangani for allowing the researcher to the conduct the study in Malapatan 1 District; To all Elementary School Principals of Malapatan 1 District headed by Ma'am Glenda L. Elem, the Public Schools District Supervisor, for granting permission to conduct

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (79-98), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

this study; To all elementary school teachers of Malapatan 1 District for their overwhelming accommodation and cooperation during the online survey/conduct of this study; To his beloved wife and daughter, Mrs. Cheery May Danielle P. Dubalan and Jaynielle Joy P. Dubalan, who had given their unconditional love, courage and moral support and who have been his inspirations to go on with the study despite of all circumstances and challenges in his life. Most of all, to Almighty God for giving him the sustained strength, determination, and boundless guidance from the start up to the end of this study.

8. About the Author(s)

Jay-ar M. Dubalan is a public school teacher of the Sarangani Division, Region XII, Philippines.

REFERENCES

- [1] Agayi, L. (2015). Teachers' needs and predesigned instructional practices: an analysis of a reading/language arts coursebook for a second grade class Available: <http://www.highbeam.com/doc/1G1-142874178.html> Retrieved: September 5, 2019
- [2] Ansari, U., Malik S. (2013). Image of an effective teacher in the 21st century classroom. *Journal of Educational and International Studies in the World*, Vol 3, Issue no 4, ISSN 2146- 7463
- [3] Askandar , K. D. , Kadtong , M.L. , Usop , A.M. (2013). "Work performance and job satisfaction among teachers". *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*.
- [4] Aubusson, P., Brady, L., Dinham S., (2005) *Action learning: What works?* University of Technology, University of Wollongong pp. 10-93
- [5] Biggs, J., Lam R., (1997) *Enhancing teaching through action learning; helping innovation in Hongkong*, University of Hongkong, pp 2- 10
- [6] Brunett , E.N. (2012). *The educational theory of Lev Vygotsky: An analysis*. New Foundations.
- [7] Burton, T. (2015), *Exploring the impact of teacher collaboration on teacher learning and development*. University of South Carolina - Columbia, Thesis, pp. 5-92
- [8] Carter. R. and D. Nunan (2012) *The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [9] *Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers Manual* (1997).
- [10] Cropper, B., Dick, B., Donaldson, B., and Patty, C. (2002). *Learning from action*, Brisbane, Qld.: Department of Families. pp. 10- 32
- [11] Dadaso (2017) *The importance of continuing professional development*. Retrieved April 4, 2020 from <http://deped.in/VPwRBGh>
- [12] Deakin Crick, R. (2008). *Pedagogy for citizenship*. In European Commission 2013, *Supporting teacher competence development for better learning outcomes*
- [13] Department of Education and Training (2005), *Professional learning in effective schools, the seven principles of highly effective professional learning* Published by Leadership and Teacher Development Branch Office of School Education Department of Education & Training Melbourne July 2005 <http://www.sofweb.vic.edu.au/blueprint/fs5/default.asp>
- [14] DepED Order No. 36, s. 2013) *Our Department of Education Vision, Mission and Core Values (DepEd VMV)* Retrieved May 15, 2020 from <http://deped.in/pAJumCE>
- [15] DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017. *National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers* Retrieved May 8, 2020 From <http://deped.in/YgSDBIs>

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (79-98), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [16] DepED Order No. 32, s. 2009 National Adoption and Implementation of NCBTS TSNA and IPPD for Teachers, and Integration of its System Operations in The Overall Program for Continuing Teacher Capacity Building Retrieved May 2, 2020 from <http://deped.in/Q0Ch38v>
- [17] DepED Order No. 2 series 2015. Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of RPMS, retrieved April 2, 2020 from <http://deped.in/9MwaNjX>
- [18] Epstein, R. M., & Hundert, E. M. (2002). Defining and assessing professional competence. *JAMA: Journal of the American Medical Association*, 287, 226 –235
- [19] European Commission (2013). Supporting teacher competence development for better learning outcomes, http://ec.europa.eu/education/school_education/teacher-cluster_en.hm.
- [20] Goddard, Y. L., & Goddard, R. D. (2007). A theoretical and empirical investigation of teacher collaboration for school improvement and student achievement in public elementary schools. *Teacher College Record*, 109(4), pp. 877-896.
- [21] Goodrum, D., Hackling, M., & Rennie, L. (2013). The status and quality of teaching and learning of science in Australian schools. Canberra: Department of Education, Training and Youth Affairs
- [22] Groh (2017) Effective Teacher Professional Development Retrieved May 12, 2020 from <http://deped.in/oCSLPMK>
- [23] Guevara, I., V. Nuqui, A. (2016). LCUP Administrator and Teachers Training Needs Assessment: Basis for Developing a Faculty Development Program, *Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 2(1). 1-14.
- [24] Hagger, H. & McIntyre, D. (2006). Learning teaching from teachers. Realizing the potential of school-based teacher education. Maidenhead: Open University Press.
- [25] Johnson, N. (2003). Perspectives on education. working in teams, pp. 4-20 Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Student Teachers. *The Mathematics Educator*, Volume 10 (2), pp 27-54 Manual on Regulations for Private Schools, 2010.
- [26] Kasmie, G. (2013). In-service Training of Secondary Level Teachers : A Follow Up of Teachers' Performance in Comparative Perspective, *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol.2, No.11 & 12
- [27] Kwong, C.W., Joseph, Y.K.K., Eric, C.C.M & Khoh, L.S. (2014). Development of Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Student Teachers. *The Mathematics Educator*, Volume 10 (2), pp 27-54 Manual on Regulations for Private Schools, 2014.
- [28] Lasaten, R.C. (2016). Assessment Methods, Problems and Training Needs of Public High School Teachers in English, *International Journal of Languages, Literature and Linguistics*, Vol. 2, No. 2, June 2016
- [29] Liakopoulou, M. (2011) The professional competence of teachers: which qualities, attitudes, skills and knowledge contribute to a teacher's effectiveness? *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Vol.1 No. 21 [Special Issue December 2011.
- [30] Little, Judith. 2003. Professional community and the problem of high reform. *International Journal of Education Research* 37 (8), 693-714.
- [31] Manual on Regulations for Private Schools, 2012. Curriculum Planning Development Division.
- [32] Marquardt, M.J (2004). Optimizing the power of action learning, solving problems and building leaders in real time, Vol. 26, No. 8, Part 2, pp. 2-8
- [33] McBer, H. (2000). Research into teacher effectiveness: a model of teacher Effectiveness .Research Report pp. 216. OECD (2011) Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and the Teaching Profession
- [34] Mizell, P. (2012). Professional Learning in the Academe. *Journal of Education*.
- [35] Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J., (2014). Introducing TPCK. In AACTE Committee on Innovation and Technology (Ed.), *The handbook of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK) for educators* (pp. 3-29). New York, NY: Rutledge. Retrieved from webcache.googleusercontent.com

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (79-98), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [36] Moe, M.S. (2012). Learning, knowing and doing classroom assessment: exposure and understanding rates of assessment knowledge among elementary pre-service teachers. University of Iowa.
- [37] Nem Singh, R. P., & Padilla, C. P. (2012). Innovative teaching and evaluation. Mandaluyong City, National Book Store.
- [38] Non, S.P. (2012). "Teachers' instructional competencies and school effectiveness of selected schools of General Santos City". Mindanao State University- General Santos City. Unpublished Masteral Thesis.
- [39] OECD (2009). Creating effective teaching and learning environments. First results from TALIS. Paris: OECD Publications <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/17/51/43023606.pdf>
- [40] Pascual (2018) Level of Implementation of the Results-based Performance Management System in the Department of Education-Philippines Retrieved from April 23, 2020 from <http://deped.in/hTdg1b6>
- [41] Poulos, J. (2013) School on the Move, Rennie Center for Education Research & Policy, Edvestors, pp.3-24
- [42] Raelin, J. (2000) Work-based Learning, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle, NJ, pp. 66
- [43] Revans, R (1979). Action learning, management decision. Journal Volume.1 Issue 1
- [44] Riemers, E.V. (2003). Teacher professional development: an international review of the literature. UNESCO: International Institute for Educational Planning Available: <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0013/001330/133010e.pdf> Retrieved: September 11, 2019
- [45] Ronfeldt, M., Farmer, S., McQueen, K., & Grissom, J. (2015). Teacher collaboration in instructional teams and student achievement. American Educational Research Journal, 52(3), 475-514.
- [46] Ronfeldt, M., Farmer, S., McQueen, K., & Grissom, J. (2015). Teacher collaboration in instructional teams and student achievement. American Educational Research Journal, 52(3), 475-514.
- [47] Ruebling, D. (2007). Action learning, creating the connection between good intentions and great execution. January/February 2007 Gama International Journal pp. 1-3
- [48] Salandron, J. (2012). "Development of professional identity among professional development school pre-service teachers: longitudinal and comparative analysis". In: Action in Teacher Education, 22(2A), 63-72.
- [49] SEAMEO Innotech Regional Project Series (SIREP) 2009. Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization. Regional Center for Educational Innovation and Technology. Commonwealth Avenue Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines. Retrieved from www.seameo-innotech.org.
- [50] SEAMEO INNOTECH (2010) Teaching competency standards in southeast asian countries, SIREP (SEAMEO INNOTECH Regional Education Project Series) Copyright 2010. <http://www.seameo-innotech.org>
- [51] Williams, M.L. (2010). Teacher collaboration as professional development in a large, suburban high school. College of Education and Human Sciences. Retrieved on January 17, 2020 from: <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cehdsdiss>
- [52] Vermunt (2014) Classroom management influence student learning environment and student learning outcome Retrieved May 18, 2020 from <http://deped.in/ZMhxsKy>
- [53] ILO/UNESCO. 1966. Recommendations concerning the status of teachers.
- [54] Stronge, James. 2007. Qualities of effective teachers (2nd Ed.). Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- [55] Unay, O Dg. (2019). Secondary School Teachers' Training Needs Assessment in Mondragon Northern Samar: Basis for Extension Program of the College of Science, University of Eastern Philippines. Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456- 6470, Volume-3 | Issue-4, June 2019, pp.339-342, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23750.pdf>
- [56] UNESCO ISO. 2006. Teachers and educational quality.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (79-98), Month: May - June 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [57] UNESCO. 2014. EFA Global Monitoring Report Teaching and Learning: Achieving quality for all.
- [58] Whitehouse, Claire. 2011. Effective continuing professional development for teachers. Manchester, UK: Center for Education Research and Quality
- [59] Yson (2017) Problems Encountered Among Teachers on RPMS: Inputs for Teachers Enhancement Program retrieved from Retrieved from <http://deped.in/HJGsOgz>
- [60] Mager, R. F., & Pipe, P. (2012). Analysing performance problems. Belmont: Lake Publishing
- [61] McGehee, W., & Thayer, P. W. (2012). Training in business and industry. New York: Wiley.
- [62] Clarke, N. (2013). The politics of training needs analysis. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 15(4), 141-153. doi: 10.1108/13665620310474598
- [63] Muijs, D., & Reynolds, D. (2005). *Effective teaching: Evidence and Practice*. London: Paul Chapman Publishing.